

**CORPORATE GOVERNANCE, RISK MANAGEMENT AND OPERATIONS CONTROL
PRACTICES OF THE INSTITUTIONAL MEMBER COOPERATIVES OF THE
ZAMBOANGA DEL NORTE COOPERATIVE BANK:
BASES FOR A DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the extent of implementation of corporate governance measures, risk management systems, and operations control practices of the institutional member cooperatives of the bank, according to the evaluation of the Board of Directors, committees, and individual members to design a development program. A descriptive survey research design was used in this study. Questionnaires were used as the main instruments of data collection. These questionnaires were validated before they were distributed to 420 Board of Directors, committee members, and individual members of the institutional member cooperatives. The measures for corporate governance were taken to a moderate extent, risk management systems were implemented to a moderate extent, and operations control practices were implemented in the member cooperatives to a moderate extent. There was a significant correlation between corporate governance along the implementation of feedback systems, risk management systems, loss financing, and internal risk reduction. There was a significant correlation between corporate governance along the implementation of organizational strategies, statement of success indicators, and performance monitoring. There was also a significant correlation between corporate governance along the implementation of feedback systems, performance

monitoring, and deviation from standards. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher designed a development program entitled “Cooperatives for the Revitalization of Economic Endeavor for Development,” (CREED), which was composed of a series of brainstorming sessions that will solicit from the participants useful ideas for enriching a written development program.

Keywords: *Corporate Governance, Risk Management, Operations Control Practices, Institutional Member Cooperatives, Cooperative Bank*

INTRODUCTION

The capability of the cooperative movement to promote economic stability and development in the community has encouraged people to form cooperatives. For this reason, the residents of Dipolog City have become so convinced of the economic importance of cooperatives. However, not all cooperatives have been actively operating. Despite the problems arising in connection with the operation of cooperatives, the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank was established. The shareholders of the bank are cooperatives throughout the province of Zamboanga del Norte. The Cooperative Bank takes the responsibility of ensuring its sustainability as well as that of the member cooperatives.

Although there have been studies about corporate governance and its effective mechanism in running and managing business operations, this research endeavor explored the specific relationship between corporate governance, risk management, and operations control practices within institutional member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank. This investigated how these practices interact and influence each other, as well as their impact on the overall performance and sustainability of the cooperatives.

In the performance of its function of monitoring the operations of member cooperatives, the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank management has realized the importance of appropriate governance, risk management system, and operations control practices in the cooperatives. While it is true that the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank provides technical guidance to cooperatives, valid and reliable data are still needed so that the management of the bank can institute measures and provide the necessary advice for ensuring the viability and sustainability of its member cooperatives. Data can be available mainly through scientific and objective research. For this reason, this study is conducted. The identification of bases for a development program suggests that there is a recognized need for improvement or enhancement in these areas. Conducting the study now can help in timely intervention and support the formulation of targeted strategies to address any gaps or challenges identified.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine the extent of implementation of corporate governance measures, risk management systems, and operations control practices of the institutional member cooperatives of the bank, according to the evaluation

of the Board of Directors, Committees, and individual members to design a development program.

The following subproblems comprised the guidelines for conducting the study:

1. To what extent have the following corporate governance measures been implemented in the institutional member cooperatives of the bank:
 - 1.1. Goal-Setting Mechanisms;
 - 1.2. Organizational Strategies;
 - 1.3. Administrative Policies and Procedures; and
 - 1.4. Feedback Systems?
2. To what extent have the following risk management systems been implemented in the institutional member cooperatives:
 - 2.1 Risk Control;
 - 2.2 Loss Financing; and
 - 2.3 Internal Risk Reduction?
3. To what extent have the following operations control practices been implemented in the institutional member cooperatives:
 - 3.1 Statement of Success Indicators;
 - 3.2 Performance Monitoring; and
 - 3.3 Correction of Deviation from Standards?
4. Is there a significant correlation between:
 - 4.1 the corporate governance systems and risk management measures of the institutional member cooperatives; and
 - 4.2 the corporate governance systems and the operations control practices of the institutional member cooperatives?
5. Based on the findings of the study, how may a development program for institutional member cooperatives of the bank be designed?

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research design was used in this study to describe the measures of corporate governance, implementation of risk management systems, and operations and control practices.

The respondents of the study were the Board of Directors, committees, and individual members of 28 institutional member cooperatives throughout the province of Zamboanga del Norte. Out of the 1,400 population, 420 or 30 percent were the actual number of respondents. Having an average of 7 directors per cooperative, 5 were selected; with an average of 9 committees, 5 were taken; and 5 members were also chosen from each cooperative using purposive sampling from the respondents. The individual members were chosen according to their consistency of attendance as members from the date of the founding of the cooperative.

Three questionnaires were used as the main instruments of data collection. The Corporate Governance Evaluation Questionnaire, the Risk Management System Evaluation, Questionnaire, and the Operations and Control Practices Evaluation Questionnaires all consist of questions that are on a 5-point Likert scale with 5 = Great Extent as the highest and 1 = Never as the lowest. These questionnaires were presented

to three experts from the Cooperative Development Authority, the City Cooperative Officer of Dipolog City, and an official of the Land Bank of Philippines, to make a critique of the questionnaires used in this study. Subsequently, to determine the functionality of the questionnaires used in this study, the researcher conducted a dry run among forty members of the cooperatives based in Dipolog City. Each of the questionnaires was described here.

The Corporate Governance Evaluation Questionnaire. This questionnaire was used to evaluate the corporate governance of the institutional member cooperatives of the bank. The questionnaire contains four questions. Each question is followed by several items. Corresponding to each item are numeric scales with the following qualitative equivalents:

5 – Very Great Extent (VGE) means that the corporate governance measures of the institutional member cooperatives are conducive in all cases to the attainment of its goals and objectives. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 4.21 – 5.00 would fall under this category.

4 – Great Extent (GE) means that the corporate governance measures of the institutional member cooperatives are conducive in the majority of cases to the attainment of its goals and objectives. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 3.41 – 4.20 would fall under this category.

3 – Moderate Extent (ME) means that the corporate governance measures of the institutional member cooperatives are conducive in half of the cases to the attainment of its goals and objectives. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 2.61 – 3.40 would fall under this category.

2 – Less Extent (LE) means that the corporate governance measures of the shareholder cooperatives are conducive in a few cases to the attainment of its goals and objectives. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 1.81 – 2.60 would fall under this category.

1 – Never (N) means that the corporate governance measures of the institutional member cooperatives are not conducive to the attainment of its goals and objectives. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 1.00 – 1.80 would fall under this category.

The Risk Management System Evaluation Questionnaire. This questionnaire was used to evaluate the extent to which systems of risk management have been implemented in the institutional member cooperatives of the bank. This questionnaire contains three questions. Each question is followed by several items. Corresponding to each item are numeric scales with the following qualitative equivalents:

5 – Very Great Extent (VGE) means that the procedures and processes for averting and encountering crisis are implemented in all cases. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 4.21 – 5.00 would fall under this category.

4 – Great Extent (GE) means that the procedures and processes for averting and encountering crisis are implemented in the majority of cases. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 3.41 – 4.20 would fall under this category.

3 – Moderate Extent (ME) means that the procedures and processes for averting and encountering crisis are implemented in half of the cases. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 2.61 – 3.40 would fall under this category.

2 – Less Extent (LE) means that the procedures and processes for averting and encountering crisis are implemented in a few cases. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 1.81 – 2.60 would fall under this category.

1 – Never (N) means that the procedures and processes for averting and encountering crisis are not at all implemented. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 1.00 – 1.80 would fall under this category.

The Operations Control Practices Evaluation Questionnaire. This questionnaire was used to evaluate the implementation of the procedures and mechanics of setting the standards of performance of people and the observance of the policies, rules, and regulations of the institutional member cooperatives of the bank. Each question is followed by several possible responses. Corresponding to each possible responses are numeric scales with the following qualitative equivalents:

5 – Very Great Extent (VGE) means that the procedures and mechanics of setting the standards of performance of people and the observance of the policies, rules, and regulations of the member cooperatives are implemented in all cases. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 4.21 – 5.00 would fall under this category.

4 – Great Extent (GE) means that the procedures and mechanics of setting the standards of performance of people and the observance of the policies, rules, and regulations of the member cooperatives are implemented in the majority of cases. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 3.41 – 4.20 would fall under this category.

3 – Moderate Extent (ME) means that the procedures and mechanics of setting the standards of performance of people and the observance of the policies, rules, and regulations of the member cooperatives are implemented in half of the cases. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 2.61 – 3.40 would fall under this category.

2 – Less Extent (LE) means that the procedures and mechanics of setting the standards of performance of people and the observance of the policies, rules, and regulations of the member cooperatives are implemented in a few cases. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 1.81 – 2.60 would fall under this category.

1 – Never (N) means that the procedures and mechanics of setting the standards of performance of people and the observance of the policies, rules, and regulations of the member cooperatives are not at all implemented. In the computation of the weighted mean, the result ranging from 1.00 – 1.80 would fall under this category.

The respondents were instructed to encircle the numeral which best represents their response to each item. The researcher gave instructions to the respondents by encircling the number that corresponds to their answer to every question. Each of the instruments was accomplished by 140 Board of Directors, 140 committee members, and also 140 individual members of the institutional member cooperatives.

Weighted mean was used to describe the extent to which corporate governance measures have been implemented, the extent to which risk management systems have been implemented, and the extent to which operations control practices have been implemented in the institutional member cooperatives. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine whether or not there were significant relationships between the extent to which corporate governance measures have been implemented and the extent to which risk management systems and operations and

control practices have been implemented. The relationship was tested at .05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The extent of implementation of corporate governance measures along with goal setting is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The Extent of Implementation of Corporate Governance Measures along with Goal Setting

Goal Setting Measures	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Increasing the capitalization of the cooperative	3.74	GE	3.76	GE	3.63	GE	3.71	GE
Increasing the assets or resources of the cooperative	3.50	GE	3.57	GE	3.41	GE	3.49	GE
Declaring dividends for its members	3.54	GE	3.63	GE	3.59	GE	3.59	GE
Increasing the earnings of the cooperative	3.63	GE	3.56	GE	3.43	GE	3.54	GE
Encouraging thrift and savings among their members	3.46	GE	3.39	ME	3.30	ME	3.38	ME
Providing social (i.e., mortuary) services to its members	2.95	ME	2.89	ME	2.96	ME	2.93	ME
Increasing the volume of business of the cooperative	3.30	ME	3.36	ME	3.23	ME	3.30	ME
Extending credit services to its members	3.98	GE	3.81	GE	3.71	GE	3.83	GE
Factor Average	3.51	GE	3.50	GE	3.41	GE	3.47	GE
1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)			1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)					
2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)					
4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)								

The extent of implementation of corporate governance measures along with organizational strategies is shown in Table 2.

Table 2

The Extent of Implementation of Corporate Governance Measures along with Organizational Strategies

Organizational Strategies	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Establishing appropriate management set-up to include the manager, cashier, bookkeeper, etc.	3.76	GE	3.64	GE	3.60	GE	3.67	GE
Providing trainings annually to directors, committees, and employees	3.05	ME	3.08	ME	3.11	ME	3.08	ME
Allocating annually the statutory reserves for stability of the cooperative	3.50	GE	3.41	GE	3.29	ME	3.40	ME
Adopting innovations in implementing cooperative services	3.31	ME	3.33	ME	3.27	ME	3.30	ME
Implementing an annual or continuous capital build-up scheme	3.57	GE	3.46	GE	3.56	GE	3.53	GE
Adopting the latest technology (i.e., use of computers, etc.) in the processing of transactions	2.98	ME	3.18	ME	3.06	ME	3.07	ME
Implementing continuous membership expansion	3.16	ME	3.26	ME	3.17	ME	3.20	ME
Factor Average	3.33	ME	3.34	ME	3.29	ME	3.32	ME

1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)

2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)

4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)

1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)

3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)

The extent of implementation of corporate governance measures along with administrative policies and procedures is shown in Table 3.

Table 3

The Extent of Implementation of Corporate Governance Measures along with Administrative Policies and Procedures

Organizational Strategies	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale

Establishing appropriate management set-up to include the manager, cashier, bookkeeper, etc.	3.76	GE	3.64	GE	3.60	GE	3.67	GE
Providing trainings annually to directors, committees, and employees	3.05	ME	3.08	ME	3.11	ME	3.08	ME
Allocating annually the statutory reserves for stability of the cooperative	3.50	GE	3.41	GE	3.29	ME	3.40	ME
Adopting innovations in implementing cooperative services	3.31	ME	3.33	ME	3.27	ME	3.30	ME
Implementing an annual or continuous capital build-up scheme	3.57	GE	3.46	GE	3.56	GE	3.53	GE
Adopting the latest technology (i.e., use of computers, etc.) in the processing of transactions	2.98	ME	3.18	ME	3.06	ME	3.07	ME
Implementing continuous membership expansion	3.16	ME	3.26	ME	3.17	ME	3.20	ME
Factor Average	3.33	ME	3.34	ME	3.29	ME	3.32	ME

1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)

2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)

4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)

1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)

3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)

The extent of implementation of corporate governance measures along with feedback systems is shown in Table 4.

Table 4

The Extent of Implementation of Corporate Governance Measures along with Feedback Systems

Feedback Systems	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Soliciting feedback through conferences with subordinates	3.10	ME	3.26	ME	2.96	ME	3.11	ME
Soliciting feedback from subordinates by making them accomplish questionnaires	2.61	ME	2.84	ME	2.75	ME	2.73	ME
Inviting subordinates to send feedback about the cooperative's practices	2.79	ME	2.91	ME	2.71	ME	2.80	ME

Soliciting the subordinate's feedback about their evaluation results	2.80	ME	2.93	ME	2.76	ME	2.83	ME
Soliciting feedback from the members about the cooperative's services	3.09	ME	3.03	ME	2.84	ME	2.99	ME
Using the employees' feedback to improve supervisory practices	3.14	ME	3.13	ME	2.98	ME	3.08	ME
Using the members' feedback to improve the cooperative's services	3.20	ME	3.13	ME	2.95	ME	3.09	ME
Supporting and encouraging the continual flow of feedback from employees and members	3.15	ME	3.10	ME	3.01	ME	3.09	ME
Factor Average	2.98	ME	3.04	ME	2.87	ME	2.96	ME

1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)

2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)

4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)

1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)

3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)

The summary of the extent of implementation of corporate governance measures is shown in Table 5.

Table 5

The Summary of the Extent of Implementation of Corporate Governance Measures

Governance Dimensions	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Goal Setting	3.51	GE	3.50	GE	3.41	GE	3.47	GE
Organizational Strategies and Procedures	3.33	ME	3.34	ME	3.29	ME	3.32	ME
Administrative Policies	3.15	ME	3.14	ME	3.02	ME	3.10	ME
Feedback Systems	2.98	ME	3.04	ME	2.87	ME	2.96	ME
General Average	3.24	ME	3.25	ME	3.15	ME	3.21	ME

1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)

2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)

4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)

1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)

3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)

The extent of implementation of risk management systems along with risk control is shown in Table 6.

Table 6*The Extent of Implementation of Risk Management Systems along with Risk Control*

Indicators	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Considering the borrower's capacity to pay in extending credit	3.88	GE	3.82	GE	3.69	GE	3.80	GE
Considering the member's capital investment as a basis for the amount of loan	3.68	GE	3.61	GE	3.60	GE	3.63	GE
Hiring a collector to monitor, follow-up, and make actual collections	2.79	ME	2.76	ME	2.78	ME	2.78	ME
Automatically deviating from an original plan (Plan A) by adopting an alternative plan (Plan B) to cope with economic crisis	3.10	ME	3.07	ME	3.16	ME	3.11	ME
Fixing a maximum loanable amount to a single borrower	3.62	GE	3.56	GE	3.42	GE	3.53	GE
Instituting legal action for delinquent and non-paying borrowers	2.84	ME	3.01	ME	3.13	ME	2.99	ME
Accelerating the collection of receivables to avoid financial crisis	3.38	ME	3.38	ME	3.32	ME	3.36	ME
Enforcing stricter measures for screening loan applicants	3.41	GE	3.47	GE	3.37	ME	3.42	GE
Factor Average	3.34	ME	3.34	ME	3.31	ME	3.33	ME
1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)			1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)					
2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)					
4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)								

The extent of implementation of risk management systems along with loss financing is shown in Table 7.

Table 7*The Extent of Implementation of Risk Management Systems along with Loss Financing*

Indicators	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale

Establishing a Retirement Fund (RF) for employees of the cooperative	2.33	LE	2.46	LE	2.58	LE	2.46	LE
Allocating annually an Optional Fund (OF) of the cooperative	2.90	ME	2.83	ME	2.87	ME	2.87	ME
Allocating annually for Education and Training Fund (ETF) to finance training expenses of the cooperative	3.27	ME	3.15	ME	3.26	ME	3.23	ME
Allocating annually for Reserve Fund (RF) to absorb possible losses on operations	3.42	GE	3.29	ME	3.23	ME	3.31	ME
Providing an Allowance for Bad Debts to absorb possible losses on loans	2.92	ME	2.83	ME	2.84	ME	2.86	ME
Requiring a bond of accountable (i.e., cashier, treasurer) officers of the cooperative	3.33	ME	2.96	ME	3.26	ME	3.18	ME
Covering the borrowers by a loan insurance protection in case of death	2.81	ME	2.81	ME	2.79	ME	2.80	ME
Covering facilities and equipment by an insurance	2.65	ME	2.60	ME	2.65	ME	2.63	ME
Factor Average	2.95	ME	2.87	ME	2.93	ME	2.92	ME
1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)					1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)			
2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)					3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)			
4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)								

The extent of implementation of risk management systems along with internal risk reduction is shown in Table 8.

Table 8

The Extent of Implementation of Risk Management Systems along with Internal Risk Reduction

Strategies	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Submitting the cooperative to a yearly audit by the Audit and Inventory Committee (AIC)	3.81	GE	3.58	GE	3.62	GE	3.67	GE
Analyzing the financial statements and other								

monthly data to detect potential problems	3.74	GE	3.53	GE	3.57	GE	3.61	GE
Observing proper internal (i.e., fraud) control systems in the cooperative	3.61	GE	3.49	GE	3.50	GE	3.53	GE
Providing the employees with appropriate insurance (i.e., SSS, etc.) coverage as required by law	2.70	ME	2.61	ME	2.65	ME	2.65	ME
Giving salaries to employees with the minimum as required by law	2.86	ME	2.82	ME	2.98	ME	2.89	ME
Mentoring selected employees to fill up future vacancies in technical positions	2.77	ME	2.73	ME	2.90	ME	2.80	ME
Monitoring conflict of business interest within the board, management and staff	3.17	ME	3.06	ME	3.15	ME	3.13	ME
Engaging in diversified (i.e., multi-purpose) cooperative services and activities	3.15	ME	3.10	ME	3.09	ME	3.11	ME
Factor Average	3.23	ME	3.11	ME	3.18	ME	3.17	ME

1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)

2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)

4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)

1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)

3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)

The summary of the extent of implementation of risk management systems is shown in Table 9.

Table 9

The Summary of the Extent of Implementation of Risk Management Systems

Risk Management Systems	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Risk Control Measures	3.34	ME	3.34	ME	3.31	ME	3.33	ME
Loss Financing	2.95	ME	2.87	ME	2.93	ME	2.92	ME
Internal Risk Reduction	3.23	ME	3.11	ME	3.18	ME	3.17	ME

General Average	3.17	ME	3.11	ME	3.14	ME	3.14	ME
1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)			1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)					
2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)					
4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)								

The extent of implementation of operations control practices along with statement of success indicators is shown in Table 10.

Table 10

The Extent of Implementation of Operations Control Practices along with Statement of Success Indicators

Control Systems	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Requiring an increase in the profits of the cooperative by ten to fifteen percent as compared to the previous year	3.26	ME	3.22	ME	3.22	ME	3.23	ME
Requiring an increase in assets by more than twenty five percent as compared to the previous year	3.04	ME	3.01	ME	3.03	ME	3.03	ME
Targeting a reserve fund of more than ten percent of net surplus	3.14	ME	3.18	ME	3.18	ME	3.17	ME
Requiring an increase in the number of members and/or clientele by more than twenty percent as compared to the previous year	2.87	ME	2.95	ME	3.08	ME	2.97	ME
Maintaining a past due rate of not more than twenty five percent	2.94	ME	2.96	ME	2.95	ME	2.95	ME
Targeting an increase in capital to at least twenty five percent as compared to the previous year	3.01	ME	3.08	ME	3.00	ME	3.03	ME
Requiring a decrease in the operating cost of the cooperative by five percent as compared to the previous year	3.05	ME	3.02	ME	2.92	ME	3.00	ME
Maintaining a collection rate of at least seventy five percent of the amounts due and collectible	3.17	ME	3.13	ME	3.12	ME	3.14	ME
Factor Average	3.06	ME	3.07	ME	3.06	ME	3.06	ME

1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)
 2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)
 4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)

1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)
 3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)

The extent of implementation of operations control practices along with performance monitoring is shown in Table 11.

Table 11

The Extent of Implementation of Operations Control Practices along with Performance Monitoring

Control Practices	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average Scale	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Submitting the cooperative to performance and fiscal audit by an external auditor (i.e., CPA)	3.55	GE	3.41	GE	3.43	GE	3.46	GE
Conducting a semi-annual performance evaluation of employees	3.01	ME	2.88	ME	3.05	ME	2.98	ME
Monitoring the trend of members' patronage to cooperative services	3.33	ME	3.35	ME	3.22	ME	3.30	ME
Monitoring the amortization payments of member borrowers	3.45	GE	3.38	ME	3.35	ME	3.39	ME
Monitoring compliance of the by-laws, rules, and regulations of the cooperative	3.41	GE	3.43	GE	3.38	ME	3.41	GE
Monitoring submission and compliance of annual reports and audited financial statements to the CDA	3.60	GE	3.45	GE	3.47	GE	3.51	GE
Identifying active and inactive members of the cooperative	3.44	GE	3.42	GE	3.45	GE	3.44	GE
Factor Average	3.40	ME	3.33	ME	3.34	ME	3.36	ME

1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)

2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)

4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)

1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)

3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)

The extent of implementation of operations control practices along with correction of deviation from standards is shown in Table 12.

Table 12

The Extent of Implementation of Operations Control Practices along with Correction of Deviation from Standards

Control Practices	Board Members n = 140		Committees n = 140		Individual Members n = 140		Item Average	
	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale	μ	Scale
Suggesting techniques of collecting the obligations of individual members	3.49	GE	3.34	ME	3.34	ME	3.39	ME
Requesting that all committees regularly perform their functions	3.50	GE	3.43	GE	3.50	GE	3.48	GE
Requiring the members to attend the Pre-Membership Education Seminar on cooperative	3.59	GE	3.36	ME	3.41	GE	3.45	GE
Proposing sanctions for directors and officers who neglect their duties	3.23	ME	3.10	ME	3.13	ME	3.15	ME
Correcting the ways in which records are kept by the cooperative	3.49	GE	3.32	ME	3.26	ME	3.36	ME
Imposing penalties for non-attendance to membership meetings	3.15	ME	2.84	ME	2.92	ME	2.97	ME
Suggesting ways of terminating directors or officers whose pecuniary interests are in conflict with their duties toward the cooperative	3.06	ME	2.97	ME	2.94	ME	2.99	ME
Factor Average	3.36	ME	3.19	ME	3.21	ME	3.25	ME
1.00 – 1.80 Never (N)			1.81 – 2.60 Less Extent (LE)					
2.61 – 3.40 Moderate Extent (ME)			3.41 – 4.20 Great Extent (GE)					
4.21 – 5.00 Very Great Extent (VGE)								

The summary of the extent of implementation of operations control practices is shown in Table 13.

Implementation of Feedback Systems	6	0.707	0.857	S	0.816	S	0.853	S
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The correlation between the extent to which corporate governance measures have been implemented and the extent to which operations control practices have been implemented is shown in Table 15.

Table 15

The Correlation between the Implementation of Corporate Governance Measures and the Implementation of Operations Control Practices

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE	CORRELATES							
	OPERATIONS CONTROL PRACTICES				Deviation from Standards			
	df	Critical r	Statement of Success Computed r	Interpretation	Performance Monitoring Computed r	Interpretation	Computed r	Interpretation
Implementation of Goal Setting	6	0.707	0.519	NS	0.606	NS	0.863	S
Implementation of Organizational Strategies	5	0.754	0.784	S	0.762	S	0.634	NS
Implementation of Administrative Policies and Procedures	6	0.707	0.744	S	0.012	NS	0.642	NS
Implementation of Feedback Systems	6	0.707	0.692	NS	0.840	S	0.766	S

The following is the development program entitled “Cooperatives for the Revitalization of Economic Endeavor for Development” (CREED).

Section 1 of the development program which is about the improvement of the corporate governance of cooperatives is shown in Table 16.

Table 16

Section 1: Program for the Improvement of the Corporate Governance of Cooperatives

Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
I. Improvement of Goals	<p>I. Goals</p> <p>A. Encouragement of Thrift and Savings among Members</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Holding seminars on thrift and savings 2. Giving incentives to members who have the highest amount of savings with their cooperative and /or with the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank 3. Encouraging the members to increase their capital to the cooperative <p>B. Providing social services to the members of the cooperatives</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assigning a group of members to study the following measures to render social services to the members: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Mortuary services b. Scholarship grants to children of outstanding members of cooperatives c. Financial aid (specific amount) for members with serious ailments 	I. Year 1 – Year 5	I. Board of Directors/ Officers
Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Delegating to a committee to research on various social services intended for the members <p>C. Increasing the volume of business of the cooperatives</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engaging in a massive campaign for increasing the 		

<p>II. Restructuring of Organizational Strategies</p>	<p>membership of cooperatives</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Increasing the capital structure of the cooperatives 3. Branching out and/or opening new business segments <p>II. Strategies</p> <p>A. Annual training of directors, committees, and employees and conduct:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Seminars on the Cooperative Code of the Philippines (Year 1) 2. Seminars on the functions of directors, officers, committees and staff (Year 1) 3. Seminars on customer relations for employees (Year 1) 4. Seminars on credit management for credit committees (Year 1) 5. Seminars on work values for employees (Year 1) 6. Other cooperative and business seminars. 	<p>II. Year 1 – Year 5</p>	<p>II. Education and Training Committee</p>
<p>Project</p>	<p>Implementation Strategies</p>	<p>Time Frame</p>	<p>Persons Involved</p>
	<p>B. Annual Allocation of Statutory Reserves:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provision of Optional Fund (OF) by not more than 10% of Net Surplus 2. Provision of Reserve Fund (RF) of at least 10% of Net Surplus 3. Provision of Education and Training Fund (ETF) of not more than 10% of Net Surplus <p>C. Implementing Innovations on Services:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Updating the policies on cooperative services 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Sending managers on strategic management seminars 3. Designing strategies for competitiveness <p>D. Adopting the Latest Technology in the Processing of Transactions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acquiring, in the initial year, computer hardware and software for the various transactions of the cooperatives. 2. Setting up a management information system in the cooperatives. 3. Upgrading the software from time to time. 4. Hiring personnel who are well-versed in the use of computers. 		Board of Directors/Officers
Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
III. Improvement of Administrative Policies and Procedures	<p>E. Continuous Membership Expansion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Using the strategy of “Each One Recruits Three” and “Each of the Three Recruits Three” for the expansion of membership 2. Conducting a Pre-Membership Coop Seminar free of charge. 3. Massive information dissemination on the concepts of cooperativism <p>III. Measures</p> <p>A. Manual Writing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Drafting of the following policies and guidelines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. duties and responsibilities of employees b. recruitment and selection of personnel c. retention of employees 	III. Year 1	Board of Directors/ Committees/ Officers III. Board of Directors/ Committees/ Members

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> d. promotion of employees e. termination of personnel f. financial reward system g. retirement program of employees h. sanctions for policy violations i. use of management information system 		
Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
IV. Enhancement of Feedback Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Conducting brainstorming sessions among the Board of Directors, committees, and members for possible revision and finalization. 3. Approving the employees' manual 4. Publishing the employees' manual <p>B. Conflict Management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Holding brainstorming sessions on the techniques of conflict management 2. Revising and finalizing the policies and guidelines on management of conflict within the cooperative 3. Creation of arbitration committee to settle disputes within the cooperative <p>IV. Feedback Practices</p> <p>A. Group and Individual Meetings and Conferences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conferences will be conducted in groups to give feedback to improve supervisory practices 2. One-on-one conference with employees to clarify issues about cooperative services 	IV. Year 1 – Year 5	IV. Special Committees/ Officers
	Implementation		Persons

Project	Strategies	Time Frame	Involved
	<p>B. Survey Techniques</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Employees are made to accomplish questionnaires that facilitate their giving of feedback to their superiors. 2. A survey is made to determine the members' feedback about their respective cooperative services. 3. A survey is made to determine the employees' feedback on the ways to improve supervisory practices. 4. A survey is made to determine the subordinates' feedback about their evaluation results <p>C. Continuous Feedback System:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Encouraging employees during conferences and meetings to send feedback about cooperatives practices 2. Supporting and encouraging the continual flow of feedback from employees and members 		
Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
	<p>D. Post Evaluation Conference</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. After each evaluation, the results and suggestions are discussed with the employees. 2. The employees are encouraged to give feedback about the manner of evaluation. 		

Section 2 of the development program which is about the revitalization of risk management is shown in Table 17.

Table 17

Section 2: Program for Revitalization of Risk Management

Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
I. Improvement of Risk Control Strategies	<p>I. Specific Strategies</p> <p>A. Collection Management</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Deliberating on whether to hire a collector or assigning an employee or member to monitor, follow up, and make actual collections. 2. Engaging a lawyer on a case-to-case arrangement to institute legal action against delinquent and non-paying borrowers. 3. Accelerating the collection of receivables to avoid financial crisis <p>B. Contingency Planning</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Encouraging and promoting the formulation of alternative plans instead of relying only on one plan for the whole year. 2. Implementing the contingency plan when the original plan fails. 	I. Year 1 – Year 5	I. Board of Directors/ Officers
II. Loss Financing	<p>II. Strategies</p> <p>A. Fund Allocation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conducting meetings with the Board of Directors to deliberate on the formulation of resolutions endorsing the following measures: 	II. Regularly to be taken from Year 1 – Year 5	II. Board of Directors/ Officers
Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Reserving a Retirement Fund for the employees of the cooperative in consonance with a retirement plan which is 		

	<p>subject to approval by the Board of Directors.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Allocating an Optional Fund (OF) for any development projects and other purposes c. Allocating an adequate annual Education and Training Fund (ETF) for the enhancement of the management skills of officers and directors and the orientation of prospective members d. Allocating an adequate Reserve Fund (RF) to be used in case of losses. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Providing a fund (i.e., Allowance for Bad Debts) to cover bad debts on operations. 3. Providing a fidelity bond for accountable officers handling funds in the cooperative. 4. Drawing insurance on borrowers for protection against non-payment of loans in case of the borrowers' death 		
Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
III. Internal Risk Reduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Covering facilities, equipment, and buildings by insurance <p>III. Measures</p> <p>A. Benefits and Salaries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Providing the employees with SSS coverage. 2. Giving employees salaries in accordance with the Minimum Wage Law <p>B. Human Resource Enhancement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mentoring selected employees to fill up future vacancies in technical positions 	III. Year 1- Year 5, as the need arises	III. Board of Directors/ Officers

	<p>2. Monitoring conflict of business interest within the Board, management, and staff to protect the business of the cooperative</p> <p>C. Enhancement of Operations</p> <p>1. Conducting feasibility studies on business prospects for the cooperative</p> <p>2. Diversifying the services and entrepreneurial activities of the cooperative</p>		
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Section 3 of the development program which is about redirection of operations control is shown in Table 18.

Table 18

Section 3: Program for Redirection of Operations Control

Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
I. Setting Success Indicators	<p>I. Success Indicators</p> <p>A. Increase in Funds</p> <p>Emphasis will be placed on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Obtaining an increase in the profits of the cooperative by ten to fifteen percent as compared to the previous year Obtaining an increase in assets by more than 25% as compared to the previous year Aiming for an increase in capital by at least 25% as compared to the previous year. Maintaining a collection rate of at least seventy five percent of the amounts due and collectible <p>B. Reserve Fund</p> <p>Having a reserve fund of more than ten percent of</p>	I. Year 1 – Year 5	Board of Directors/ Officers

	<p>the net surplus</p> <p>C. Membership Increase Working for an increase in the number of members and clientele by more than 20% as compared to the previous year</p> <p>D. Control of Delinquency Maintaining a past due rate of not more than twenty-five percent</p>		
Project	Implementation Strategies	Time Frame	Persons Involved
II. Performance Monitoring	<p>E. Savings on Operation Requiring a decrease in the operating costs of the cooperative by five percent as compared to the previous year</p> <p>II. Specific Measures</p> <p>A. Employee Evaluation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Formulating and validating an evaluation instrument for employees 2. Conducting an evaluation of the employees' performance on a semi-annual schedule <p>B. Evaluation of Patronage</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Formulating and validating an instrument for studying the trend on the patronage of cooperative members 2. Conducting trend studies of loan amortization payments of cooperative borrowers 	II. Year 1 – Year 5	II. Board of Directors/ Officers
III. Correcting Deviations from Standards	<p>III. Maintenance of Standards</p> <p>A. Strategies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Designing, formulating and suggesting techniques on loan collections for implementation by management 2. Correcting the ways in which records are kept by the cooperative 	III. Year 1	III. Board of Directors
	Implementation		Persons

Project	Strategies	Time Frame	Involved
	<p>B. System of Sanctions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conducting meetings for deliberating on the sanctions to be administered on directors and officers who neglect their duties. 2. Imposing the specific sanctions on erring directors and officers 3. Imposing penalties on members who fail to attend meetings <p>C. Avoidance of Conflict of Interest</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conducting meetings to deliberate on the detection of directors or officers whose business interests are in conflict with their performance of duties toward the cooperative 2. Terminating directors and officers with pecuniary interests contrary to their duties toward the cooperative 		

DISCUSSION

Table 1 contains data regarding the extent to which the member cooperatives implemented goal-setting measures for the organization and its members.

As revealed by the factor average of 3.47 based on the group averages of 3.51 from the Board of Directors, 3.50 from the committees, and 3.41 from the individual members, the shareholder cooperatives implemented to a Great Extent goal setting measures for the organization and its members.

Specifically, measures for increasing the capitalization of the cooperative were implemented to a Great Extent, as revealed by the item average of 3.71 based on the weighted mean of 3.74 from the Board Members, 3.76 from the committees, and 3.63 from the individual members. Measures for increasing the assets or resources of the cooperative were implemented to a Great Extent, as shown by the item average of 3.49 based on the weighted mean of 3.50 from the Board Members, 3.57 from the committees, and 3.41 from the individual members. Measures for declaring dividends for its members were implemented to a Great Extent as revealed by the item average of 3.59 based on

the weighted mean of 3.54 from the Board Members, 3.63 from the committees, and 3.59 from the individual members. Measures for increasing the earnings of the cooperatives were implemented in the shareholder cooperatives, as revealed by the item average of 3.54 based on the weighted mean of 3.63 from the Board of Directors, 3.56 from the committees, and 3.43 from the individual members.

These findings revealed that in the majority of cases, the members of the cooperative bank augmented their capital to make their cooperatives more viable and profitable.

Owing to the need to accommodate the financial requirements of their individual members, the shareholder cooperatives considered it necessary to increase capitalization to best serve their members. In fact, capital adequacy was one of the major factors that would lead to the success of all business organizations including cooperatives. That's why the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas is considered as the number one criterion in rating all banks in the country.

Also, in the majority of cases, the cooperative shareholders increased their resources to be able to extend services to their members and clients. The assets of the cooperatives were increased as a result of continuous capital build-up, increase in profits, and borrowings from banks and other financial institutions. A continuous and substantial increase in assets or resources could be an indication of the cooperatives' growth and development.

In the majority of cases, dividends were declared by the shareholder cooperatives that benefited the organization and its members. Thus, the shareholders, adhered to the principle that the members should be given dividends comprising of interest on capital and patronage refunds. Such dividends were declared in the form of cash and stocks. Only cash dividends were given to the individual members as an actual return on their investment while stock dividends were added to the members' paid-up capital which resulted to the advantage of the organization.

Similarly, in the majority of cases, the member cooperatives implemented measures for increasing the income of their respective cooperatives. This was the trend because the primary objective of every business establishment was maximum profitability. That an increasing trend in earnings would mean growth and progress. In the case of the member cooperatives, they engaged in various business ventures aside from investing in the cooperative bank for sustainable operations.

As revealed by the item average of 3.38, the cooperative took measures to encourage thrift and savings among their members. The weighted mean of 3.46 from the Board of Directors revealed their perception that this measure was implemented to a Great Extent. The weighted mean of 3.39 from the committees and 3.30 from the individual members denoted their perception that these measures were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

The Board of Directors viewed the measure of encouraging thrift and savings among members as implemented to a majority of cases which was opposed to that of the committees and individual members.

The Board Members had a different response from that of the two groups because they were concerned with upholding the general principle governing cooperatives, which was the encouragement among members to save money and use it wisely. The Board of Directors, being in charge of formulating policies, and being aware of the goals of

cooperatives, viewed themselves as having attained the major goals of the movement. However, the committees and individual members revealed that there were limitations in the measures implemented by their respective cooperatives. This finding implied that if ever, thrift and savings were encouraged among members, it was only in half of the cases that measures for attaining this goal were implemented.

To a Moderate Extent, measures were implemented for providing social services, such as mortuary assistance to its members, as revealed by the item average of 2.93 based on the weighted mean of 2.95 from the Board of Directors, 2.89 from the committees, and 2.96 from the individual members, and increasing the volume of business of the cooperative, as shown by the item average of 3.30 based on the weighted mean of 3.30 from the Board of Directors, 3.36 from the committees, and 3.23 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that in half of the cases, the cooperatives helped their members in the sense that they rendered social services like financial assistance in times of accident and hospitalization and mortuary aid in case of death. Both the cooperatives and the individual members as a whole benefited to a limited extent from the measures implemented by the member cooperatives since, the accumulated mortuary and other funds intended for the purpose can generate additional income through deposit transactions with banks and at the same time can be utilized for assistance to members as the need arises. Another measure considered beneficial, though limited, was the scheme to increase the business activities of cooperatives. This limitation was attributed to the inadequacy of capital by cooperatives to undertake various business activities. The increase in the volume of business was vital to the organization's profitability and sustainability.

As revealed by the item average of 3.83 based on the weighted mean of 3.98 from the Board Members, 3.81 from the committees, and 3.71 from the individual members, measures were implemented to a Great Extent, for extending credit services to the members.

From this finding, it could be inferred that in the majority of cases, the cooperatives facilitated, among their members, the use of cash for deferred payment terms. This arrangement was helpful to them in the sense that it made cash readily available to them. This economic activity was one of the specific goals of cooperatives as embodied under Article 6 of Republic Act 6938. Goals are more likely to elicit support when they are clearly relevant to the major work of the organization and the particular work unit (Bartol and Martin, 1998).

Table 2 contains data regarding the extent to which the shareholder cooperatives implemented various organizational strategies and showed that implementation was made to a Moderate Extent, as revealed by the factor average of 3.32 based on the group average of 3.33 from the Board of Directors, 3.34 from the committees, and 3.29 from the individual members.

Specifically, as revealed by the item average of 3.67 based on the weighted mean of 3.76 from the Board of Directors, 3.64 from the committees, and 3.60 from the individual members, the cooperatives often implemented the strategy of establishing appropriate management set-up to include the manager, cashier, bookkeeper, and other personnel.

This finding revealed that in the majority of cases, the cooperatives implemented measures to promote system in the task of directing the operations of the cooperatives by means of designating specific persons to perform duties and responsibilities in order that the needed services may be rendered by them. The implementation made by the shareholders was in consonance with the provisions of the by-laws of cooperatives and in line with the practices of successful business organizations.

As revealed by the item average of 3.08 based on the weighted mean of 3.05 from the Board of Directors, 3.08 from the committees, and 3.11 from the individual members, the cooperatives provided, to a Moderate Extent, annual training to directors, committees, and employees.

From this finding, it could be inferred that in half of the cases, the cooperatives implemented measures to upgrade the capabilities of the directors, officers, committees, and employees in line with the principle of continuous cooperative education as embodied under the provisions of Republic Act 6938, otherwise known as the Cooperative Code of the Philippines. The training was done annually, however, the different sectors underwent training by turns because of the high expense incurred in the process (Interview with a Director of the Dipolog City SP Employees Multi-Purpose Cooperative).

As revealed by the item average of 3.40, the shareholder cooperatives implemented, to a Moderate Extent, measures for allocating annually for statutory reserves for the stability of the cooperatives. The weighted mean of 3.50 from the Board of Directors and 3.41 from the committees denoted their perceptions that this strategy was implemented to a Great Extent. The weighted mean of 3.29 from the individual members indicated their perception that this strategy was implemented to a Moderate Extent.

These findings resulted in the disparity of the responses of the Board of Directors and the committees on one hand and of the individual members on the other hand concerning the annual allocation of statutory reserves of cooperative shareholders. The Board of Directors and the committees indicated that the allocation of reserves was implemented in the majority of cases. On the contrary, the individual members considered that this course of action was implemented in half of the cases. This was attributed to the differences in their knowledge of the operations of their respective cooperatives. The Board of Directors and the committees were more aware than the members of the allocation of statutory reserves as mandated by the law on cooperatives.

As revealed by the item average of 3.30 based on the weighted mean of 3.31 from the Board of Directors, 3.33 from the committees, and 3.27 from the individual members, the shareholder cooperatives implemented, to a Moderate Extent, the measure of adopting innovations in implementing cooperative services.

Based on the above finding, it could be inferred that the new trends and techniques of managing cooperatives were implemented in half of the cases since they adhered mainly on cooperative laws, rules, and regulations of the Cooperative Development Authority. In other words, the cooperatives were more inclined to the implementation of the Cooperative Code, their by-laws, and cooperative principles leaving behind the strategic business practices adopted by successful corporations and other business organizations.

As indicated by the item average of 3.53 based on the weighted mean of 3.57 from the Board of Directors, 3.46 from the committees, and 3.56 from the individual members,

the shareholder cooperatives implemented to a Great Extent an annual or continuous capital build-up scheme.

Implied by this finding was the fact that in the majority of cases, the shareholder cooperatives used various strategies in augmenting the capitalization of their respective cooperatives. This was done through continuous Capital Build-up Program like the implementation of cooperatives raffle promo, capital retention on loans, and other schemes for the growth and development of the enterprise.

To a Moderate Extent, the cooperatives adopted the latest technology such as the use of computers in the processing of transactions as indicated by the item average of 3.07 based on the weighted mean of 2.98 from the Board of Directors, 3.18 from the committees, and 3.06 from the individual members, and implemented continuous membership expansion, as shown by the item average of 3.20 based on the weighted mean of 3.16 from the Board of Directors, 3.26 from the committees, and 3.17 from the individual members.

These findings revealed that in half of the cases, the cooperatives made use of modern technology for their business operations. However, as the cooperatives were still in the growth stage, they could not afford to use state-of-the-art equipment. Information and communication technologies play a significant role in enhancing organizational effectiveness by offering specific capabilities that enhance coordination, minimize information disparities, and boost productivity, as highlighted by Chattopadhyay (2013).

Table 3 contains data regarding the extent to which the shareholder cooperatives implemented specific administrative policies and procedures.

As indicated by the factor average of 3.10 based on the group average of 3.15 from the Board of Directors, 3.14 from the committees, and 3.02 from the individual members, administrative policies were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

To a Moderate Extent, the duties and responsibilities of employees were defined in a manual, as revealed by the item average of 3.32 based on the weighted mean of 3.40 from the Board of Directors, 3.35 from the committees, and 3.22 from the individual members. The policies on the recruitment and selection of cooperative employees were clearly defined to a Moderate Extent, as shown by the item average of 3.30 based on the weighted mean of 3.36 from the Board of Directors, 3.35 from the committees, and 3.19 from the individual members. The policies on the retention of cooperative employees were implemented to a Moderate Extent, as indicated by the item average of 3.23 based on the item average of 3.33 from the Board of Directors, 3.27 from the committees, and 3.10 from the individual members. The policies on the promotion of cooperative employees were implemented to a Moderate Extent, as indicated by the item average of 3.05 based on the weighted mean of 3.11 from the Board of Directors, 3.04 from the committees, and 3.00 from the individual members. The policies on the termination of the cooperative employees' services were implemented to a Moderate Extent, as disclosed by the item average of 2.99 based on the weighted mean of 3.02 from the Board of Directors, and 3.02 from the committees, and 2.93 from the individual members. The policies on the financial reward systems of the cooperatives were implemented to a Moderate Extent, as shown by the item average of 2.97 based on the weighted mean of 3.03 from the Board of Directors, 2.98 from the committees, and 2.89 from the members, and the policies on the retirement of cooperative employees were implemented to a

Moderate Extent, as shown by the item average of 2.83 based on the weighted mean of 2.88 from the Board of Directors, 2.90 from the committees, and 2.71 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that the implementation of administrative policies and procedures about staffing patterns and the definition of duties and responsibilities, recruitment and selection of employees, retention, promotion, termination, reward systems, and retirement schemes were limited in the shareholder cooperatives under study. While it was true that they implemented some of the measures in half of the cases, however, there were no written guidelines and policies for outright reference purposes according to the officers of multi-purpose cooperatives in Dipolog City. The purpose of written policies and guidelines was to guide the management in running the business operations of the cooperative especially on the aspect of human resource management.

On the aspect of dealing with policy violations of cooperative employees, it was implemented to a Moderate Extent as revealed by the item average of 3.04 based on the weighted mean of 3.01 from the Board of Directors, 3.11 from the committees, and 3.01 from the individual members. Measures for enforcing strictly the policies for the use of management information systems were implemented to a Moderate Extent, as revealed by the item average of 3.13 based on the weighted mean of 3.11 from the Board of Directors, 3.21 from the committees, and 3.06 from the individual members; and measures for managing conflict according to the guidelines set by the cooperatives were implemented to a Moderate Extent, as shown by the item average of 3.18 based on the weighted mean of 3.26 from the Board of Directors, 3.18 from the committees, and 3.09 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that decision-making on the sanctions to be imposed on policy violations could not be fully facilitated because the guidelines concerning this procedure were not clear. Administrative policies and procedures are also a part of governance. Policies are predetermined sets of guidelines to establish a definite direction in decision-making. Policies are based on the organization's vision-mission. They are formulated after a thorough analysis of organizational goals and objectives (Mondy, Sharplin, and Flippo, 1998).

Furthermore, there were no references from past actions about policy violations of employees. Regarding the use of management information systems, the policies were implemented in half of the cases. Owing to a lack of funds for the improvement of their systems, the cooperatives could not make a full implementation of their management information systems. Efforts were exerted to improve this aspect of the operation of various cooperatives, but other priorities had to be taken into consideration before its implementation.

Procedures in the management of conflict were implemented in half of the cases. However, this finding did not mean that the cooperatives ignored the incidence of conflict. The need to manage conflict was not much because according to the members of multi-purpose cooperatives in Dipolog City, the incidence of conflict was not high (interview).

Table 4 contains data on the implementation of feedback systems among the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank.

As indicated by the factor average of 2.96 based on the group average of 2.98 from the Board Members, 3.04 from the committees, and 2.87 from the individual members, feedback systems were implemented to a Moderate Extent among the member cooperatives.

Specifically, implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of soliciting feedback through conferences with subordinates, as indicated by the item average of 3.11 based on the weighted mean of 3.10 from the Board Members, 3.26 from the committees, and 2.96 from the individual members; soliciting feedback from subordinates by making them accomplish questionnaires, as indicated by the item average of 2.73 based on the weighted mean of 2.61 from the Board Members, 2.84 from the committees, and 2.75 from the individual members; inviting subordinates to send feedback about the cooperative's practices, as shown by the item average of 2.80 based on the weighted mean of 2.79 from the Board Members, 2.91 from the committees, and 2.71 from the individual members; and soliciting the subordinates' feedback about their evaluation results, as indicated by the item average of 2.83 based on the weighted mean of 2.80 from the Board Members, 2.93 from the committees, and 2.76 from the individual members.

These findings revealed that in half of the cases, comments on the systems and procedures of governance used in the cooperatives were solicited by the officers. These comments were obtained through conferences with their subordinates, which were called to a limited extent. Another way of soliciting feedback from the subordinates was by means of making them write down their comments about the system of governance and the ways in which the operations of the cooperatives were facilitated by the measures used by the officers. For this purpose, they administered questionnaires, but only to a limited extent. Regarding the practices used by the cooperatives, there were instances when the subordinates were made to send feedback, but only to a limited extent. After the regular evaluation of the employees' performance, they were invited to give their comments about the evaluation procedures and results. This practice was, however, done in half of the cases.

Also implemented to a Moderate Extent, were the measures of soliciting feedback from the members about the cooperative's services, as indicated by the item average of 2.99 based on the weighted mean of 3.09 from the Board Members, 3.03 from the committees, and 2.84 from the individual members; using the employees' feedback to improve supervisory practices, as indicated by the item average of 3.08 based on the weighted mean of 3.14 from the Board Members, 3.13 from the committees, and 2.98 from the individual members; using the members' feedback to improve the cooperative's services, as revealed by the item average of 3.09 based on the weighted mean of 3.20 from the Board Members, 3.13 from the committees, and 2.95 from the individual members; and supporting and encouraging the continual flow of feedback from employees and members, as revealed by the item average of 3.09 based on the weighted mean of 3.15 from the Board Members, 3.10 from the committees, and 3.01 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that in half of the cases, feedback was solicited regarding various practices of the cooperative. The officers solicited feedback from the members regarding their views of the services of their respective cooperatives because of their desire for improvement. In half of the cases, they used the employees'

feedback as the basis for improving their supervisory practices as well as the services. Furthermore, they supported the continuity and consistency of communication within their respective cooperatives. Still, as a whole, there was a need to improve the flow of feedback within the cooperatives. This is consistent with the results of the study by Lin, R. and Sun, B. (2018) which suggest that the enterprise should pay attention to cultivating trust among the members of the organization and maintain it, encouraging support staff feedback behavior.

Table 5 presents the summarized data on the corporate governance of member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank.

As shown by the general average of 3.21 based on the group general average of 3.24 from the Board Members, 3.25 from the committees, and 3.15 from the individual members, measures for corporate governance were taken to a Moderate Extent. Specifically, among the five dimensions of governance, there was one dimension in which measures were taken to a Great Extent.

As indicated by the factor average of 3.47 based on the group average of 3.51 from the Board Members, 3.50 from the committees, and 3.41 from the individual members, goal-setting measures were implemented in the cooperatives to a Great Extent. As evaluated by the Board Members, committees, and individual members, the measures that were implemented to a Great Extent consisted of increasing the capitalization of the cooperative, increasing the assets or resources of the cooperative, declaring dividends for its members, and increasing the earnings of the cooperative. Evaluated by the Board Members as implemented to a Great Extent and by the committees and the individual members as implemented to a Moderate Extent was the measure of encouraging thrift and savings among the members.

Evaluated by the three groups as implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of providing social services (such as mortuary aid) to its members and increasing the volume of business of the cooperative. Implemented to a Great Extent was the measure of extending credit to the members of the cooperative according to the evaluation of the Board Members, committees, and individual members.

As indicated by the factor average of 3.32 based on the group average of 3.33 from the Board Members, 3.34 from the committees, and 3.29 from the individual members, the cooperatives implemented various organizational strategies to a Moderate Extent.

The three groups of respondents viewed as implemented to a Great Extent the establishment of appropriate management set-up to include the manager, cashier, and bookkeeper and provided, to a Moderate Extent, annual training to directors, committees, and employees. Viewed by the Board of Directors and committees as implemented to a Great Extent and by the individual members as implemented to a Moderate Extent was the measure of allocating annually the statutory reserves for the stability of the cooperative. Viewed by the three groups as implemented to a Moderate Extent was the measure of adopting innovations in implementing cooperative services, and viewed as implemented to a Great Extent was the measure of implementing an annual or continuous capital build-up scheme. To a Moderate Extent, as viewed by the three groups, the measures of adopting the latest technology in the processing of transactions and the scheme of continuous membership expansion were implemented.

Administrative policies and procedures were implemented to a Moderate Extent, as disclosed by the factor average of 3.10 based on the group average of 3.15 from the Board Members, 3.14 from the committees, and 3.02 from the individual members. Viewed by the three groups as implemented to a Moderate Extent were defining clearly the duties and responsibilities of employees in a manual, defining clearly the policies on the recruitment and selection of cooperative employees, specifying the policies on the retention of cooperative employees, stating clearly the policies about the promotion of cooperative employees, and stating clearly the policies on the termination of the cooperative employees' services. Also implemented to a Moderate Extent, as viewed by the three groups of respondents, were the measures of defining clearly the policies on the financial reward systems of the cooperative, specifying the policies on the retirement of cooperative employees, dealing firmly with policy violations, enforcing strictly the policies for the use of management information systems, and managing conflict according to the guidelines set by the cooperative.

As disclosed by the factor average of 2.96 based on the weighted mean of 3.15 from the Board Members, 3.04 from the committees, and 2.87 from the individual members, feedback systems in the cooperatives were implemented to a Moderate Extent. Some of these measures included soliciting feedback through conferences with subordinates, soliciting feedback from subordinates by making them accomplish questionnaires, inviting subordinates to send feedback about the cooperative's practices, and soliciting the subordinates' feedback about their evaluation results. Also implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of soliciting feedback from the members about the cooperative's services, using the employees' feedback to improve supervisory practices, using the members' feedback to improve the cooperative's services, and supporting and encouraging the continual flow of feedback from employees and members.

Table 6 presents data on the extent to which the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank implemented risk control measures.

As disclosed by the factor average of 3.33 based on the group average of 3.34 from the Board Members, 3.34 from the committees, and 3.31 from the individual members, risk management measures were implemented to a Moderate Extent in the cooperatives which were members of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank.

Specifically, some risk control measures were implemented to a Great Extent, but more of these measures were implemented to a Moderate Extent. Implemented to a Great Extent were the measures of considering the borrower's capacity to pay in extending credit, as shown by the item average of 3.80 based on the weighted mean of 3.88 from the Board Members, 3.82 from the committees, and 3.69 from the individual members; and considering the members' capital investment as a basis for the amount of loan, as disclosed by the item average of 3.63 based on the weighted mean of 3.68 from the Board Members, 3.61 from the committees, and 3.60 from the individual members.

These findings showed that generally, in the majority of cases, the cooperatives exercised much care and prudence in extending credit to the members. They conducted a background check of the loan applicants before allowing them to borrow money from the cooperatives. Furthermore, before approving the borrowers' loan applications, they

had to determine how much was their capital investment before they could be made to borrow money from the cooperative. The purpose was to match the loan amount with the member's capacity to repay the loan.

To a Moderate Extent, measures of risk management were taken by the member cooperatives. These measures consisted of hiring a collector to monitor, follow-up, and make actual collections as shown by the item average of 2.78 based on the weighted mean of 2.79 from the Board Members, 2.76 from the committees, and 2.78 from the individual members; and automatically deviating from an original plan (Plan A) by adopting an alternative plan (Plan B) as indicated by the item average of 3.11 based on the weighted mean of 3.10 from the Board Members, 3.07 from the committees, and 3.16 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that to a limited extent, the shareholder cooperatives hired a person to collect the amortization payments of borrowers. This scheme was implemented to minimize delinquency in credit operations. Hiring field personnel was also adopted by the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank and even other financial institutions as a means of controlling non-performing loans and bad accounts. The risk was also managed in a way that not only one course of action was taken during an emergency. Planning was done in such a manner, that instead of formulating only one plan, the officers designed an alternative plan. In any eventuality, when Plan A could not be adopted, Plan B could be taken.

As revealed by the item average of 3.53 based on the weighted mean of 3.62 from the Board Members, 3.56 from the committees, and 3.42 from the individual members, the risk was managed to a Great Extent by fixing a maximum loanable amount for a single borrower.

This finding showed that in the majority of cases, the cooperatives set a specific amount as the highest value which single borrowers could be granted when they applied for loans. This control measure was implemented so that many members could borrow money at one time and also minimize the risk of non-collection. The situation of non-recovery of accounts released could be attributed to excessive availment of the borrower that impaired his capacity to pay the loan.

To a Moderate Extent, the cooperatives implemented control measures by instituting legal action for delinquent and non-paying borrowers, as indicated by the item average of 2.99 based on the weighted mean of 2.84 from the Board Members, 3.01 from the committees; and 3.13 from the individual members; and accelerating the collection of receivables to avoid financial crisis, as shown by the item average of 3.36 based on the weighted mean of 3.38 from the Board Members, 3.38 from the committees, and 3.32 from the individual members.

These findings showed that to a limited extent, the cooperatives resorted to legal remedies against borrowers who were considered problematic by not paying their matured obligations. The purpose was to protect the best interest of the investors and the cooperative organization as a whole. Furthermore, the measure was implemented so that the borrowers may know that when payments were due and demandable, the cooperatives were firm in collecting them. Also, the cooperatives showed that to a limited extent, they were efficient in the collection of loan amortizations from the members. In other words, collection efficiency in the cooperatives did not reach the standards set by banks and other financial institutions.

To a Great Extent, the cooperatives enforced stricter measures for screening loan applicants, as indicated by the item average of 3.42. The weighted mean of 3.41 from the Board Members and 3.47 from the committees showed that this measure was implemented to a Great Extent. The weighted mean of 3.37 from the individual members showed that this measure was implemented to a Moderate Extent.

Generally, the system of enforcing stricter measures for screening loan applicants was implemented in a majority of cases as viewed by the Board of Directors and committees. However, the individual members viewed that the measure was strict only to a limited extent. The stand of the Board of Directors and committees was the result of their awareness of the lending policies set by them. The purpose of adequate screening of loan applications was to avoid possible problems in the collection of accounts. Though risk management is mostly a term for the producers, within an organization, it has followed to protect itself, its staff, its clients, and its other stakeholders. It is an ongoing process and an important part of the planning of every business. Risk management should framework to reduce or eliminate the risk of certain kinds of shock on the business (Six and Kowalski, 2005).

Table 7 presents data regarding the extent to which strategies of loss financing were implemented in the member cooperatives.

As revealed by the factor average of 2.92 based on the group average of 2.95 from the Board Members, 2.87 from the committees, and 2.93 from the individual members, strategies of loss financing were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

To a Lesser Extent, the measure of establishing a Retirement Fund for the employees of the cooperative was implemented, as shown by the item average of 2.46 based on the weighted mean of 2.33 from the Board Members, 2.46 from the committees and 2.58 from the individual members.

This finding implied that only on a selective basis could additional retirement benefits be given to employees of cooperatives aside from the benefits granted by the Social Security System. Thus, there were few cases of provisions for more security in old age among the employees of cooperatives.

Any prospect of job loss before retirement age was not provided with financing; consequently, retrenched employees might not be given full benefits. The establishment of the cooperative Retirement Fund (RF) was supplementary to the benefits granted by the Social Security System upon retirement.

To a Moderate Extent, an Optional Fund (OF) was allocated annually, as shown by the item average of 2.87 based on the weighted mean of 2.90 from the Board Members, 2.83 from the committees, and 2.87 from the individual members; and there was an allocation for education and training fund to finance the training expenses of cooperatives, as denoted by the item average of 3.23 based on the weighted mean of 3.27 from the Board Members, 3.15 from the committees, and 3.26 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that to a limited extent, an Optional Fund (OF) for the construction of buildings, community development, and other purposes was allocated. The limitation of Optional Fund (OF) implied that the cooperatives could not pursue its developmental programs and projects because of financial constraints. This was attributed to the inadequate allocation of such reserve fund due to minimal earnings

of cooperatives. The cooperative law provided that the annual provision for Optional Fund (OF) should not exceed ten percent (10%) of the net surplus. In like manner, the Education and Training Fund (ETF) was allocated for the training of cooperatives; however, the amount was limited. This finding implied that with the limited amount set aside for training purposes, the cooperative movement would not be accelerated. The cooperative law also provided that the annual allocation of the Education and Training Fund (ETF) should not be more than ten percent (10%) of the net surplus of the cooperative.

As indicated by the item average of 3.31, the measure of allocating annually for the Reserve Fund (RF) to absorb possible losses on operations was implemented to a Moderate Extent. The Board Members viewed this measure as implemented to a Great Extent, as shown by the weighted mean of 3.42. The committees ($\mu = 3.29$) and the individual members ($\mu = 3.23$) viewed this measure as implemented to a Moderate Extent.

These findings revealed that to a limited extent, the cooperatives allocated a Reserve Fund (RF) that could be used for the stability of the cooperative and to meet net losses in its operations. However, the Board Members viewed this measure as implemented in the majority of cases. The disparity in the responses of the two groups could be attributed to the varying levels of knowledge of operations that the respondents possessed. The committees and the individual members regarded that reserve funds were available in half of the cases, while the Board Members viewed the reserve funds' availability in the majority of cases. The Board Members had more knowledge of the availability and sufficiency of funds than either the committees or the individual members. All of the groups knew the available amount of funds because of the financial reports, but what was sufficient from the Board Members' viewpoints was not sufficient for other respondents.

Implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of providing an Allowance for Bad Debts to absorb possible losses on loans, as revealed by the item average of 2.86 based on the weighted mean of 2.92 from the Board Members, 2.83 from the committees, and 2.84 from the individual members; requiring a bond of accountable officers of the cooperative, as shown by the item average of 3.18 based on the weighted mean of 3.33 from the Board Members, 2.96 from the committees, and 3.26 from the individual members; covering the borrowers by a loan insurance protection in case of death, as shown by the item average of 2.80 based on the weighted mean of 2.81 from the Board Members, 2.81 from the committees, and 2.79 from the individual members; and covering facilities and equipment by an insurance, as indicated by the item average of 2.63 based on the weighted mean of 2.65 from the Board Members, 2.60 from the committees, and 2.65 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that the implementation of measures to ensure against losses in the cooperatives was limited. Specifically, the provision for an amount that would cover losses caused by bad debts was limited. If for some reasons, some of the borrowers could not pay their debts, a corresponding amount was allocated for this prospect of loss to the cooperative.

For the purpose of warding off the possibility of loss in the case of mishandling funds, the cooperatives were required to secure fidelity bonds for their accountable officers and employees like the cashier, treasurer, and collectors as mandated by the Cooperative Development Authority. However, not all cooperatives had complied the

requirement. Also, to a limited extent, the cooperatives caused the coverage of a loan redemption insurance that would serve as payment for the loan in the event of the death of the borrower. However, not all cooperatives were practicing this measure. Finally, insurance coverage against damage to facilities and equipment was drawn by some cooperatives. Thus, not all cooperatives manage risk by providing for loss financing. Loss financing consists of methods used to obtain funds to pay for or offset losses that occur. Internal sources of funds to pay retained losses included cash flows from ongoing activities, general working capital, and investments in liquid assets that are dedicated to financing. Another method of financing losses is the purchase of insurance contracts (Harrington and Niehaus, 2004).

Table 8 presents data regarding the extent to which the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank implemented strategies of internal risk reduction.

As denoted by the factor average of 3.17 based on the weighted mean of 3.23 from the Board Members, 3.11 from the committees, and 3.18 from the individual members, strategies for internal risk reduction were adopted to a Moderate Extent. There were, however strategies that were implemented to a Great Extent in the cooperatives. Those that were implemented to a Great Extent were the strategies of submitting the cooperative to a yearly audit by the Audit and Inventory Committee, as shown by the item average of 3.67 based on the weighted mean of 3.81 from the Board Members, 3.58 from the committees, and 3.62 from the individual members; analyzing the financial statements and other monthly data to detect potential problems, as disclosed by the item average of 3.61 based on the weighted mean of 3.74 from the Board Members, 3.53 from the committees, and 3.57 from the individual members, and observing proper internal control (as, against fraud) in the cooperative, as indicated by the item average of 3.53 based on the weighted mean of 3.61 from the Board Members, 3.49 from the committees, and 3.50 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that in the majority of cases, the cooperatives used protective mechanisms to prevent any instance in which their funds would be depleted unnecessarily. Annual audits by internal auditors were conducted in order to determine the financial standing of the cooperatives. Through these audits, the income and expenses could be traced. The determination of cash position of the cooperatives would be facilitated.

Data within the cooperatives were used for determining the financial standing of such organizations. Among the available data were the financial statements comprising of Income Statement and Balance Sheet. These statements were analyzed in order to determine the potential problems which might be encountered by the cooperatives. Moreover, measures against fraud were also taken in the majority of cases. Internal control system were established for the purpose of safeguarding the assets and properties of the cooperatives.

Implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of providing the employees with appropriate insurance coverage as required by law, as revealed by the item average of 2.65 based on the weighted mean of 2.70 from the Board Members, 2.61 from the committees, and 2.65 from the individual members; giving salaries to employees with the minimum as required by law, as revealed by the item average of 2.89 based on the

weighted mean of 2.86 from the Board Members, 2.82 from the committees, and 2.98 from the individual members; mentoring selected employees to fill up future vacancies in technical positions, as revealed by the item average of 2.80 based on the weighted mean of 2.77 from the Board Members, 2.73 from the cooperatives, and 2.90 from the individual members; monitoring conflict of business interest within the board, the management and the staff, as disclosed by the item average of 3.13 based on the weighted mean of 3.17 from the Board Members, 3.06 from the committees, and 3.15 from the individual members; and engaging in diversified cooperative services and activities, as indicated by the item average of 3.11 based on the weighted mean of 3.15 from the Board Members, 3.10 from the committees, and 3.09 from the individual members.

These findings implied that to a limited extent, the cooperatives took measures to ensure that they would not incur voluminous expenses that would threaten their financial stability. So, to be able to help the employees in times of financial difficulties especially on the cost of hospitalization in case of accident or sickness, and to avoid legal problems for non-compliance of the law, some of the cooperatives provided their employees with insurance coverage. Thus, some of the employees of cooperatives were given Social Security System coverage.

Furthermore, the cooperatives gave salaries to employees based on the Minimum Wage Law. By means of giving their employees, this type of salary scheme, they could prevent expenses that might be incurred because of litigations that might arise if they did not comply with the law. Selected employees were subjected to training and mentoring to occupy vacant technical, supervisory, and even managerial positions. This strategy enables the cooperatives to prepare employees for succession in various positions for sustainable operations.

Another strategy to protect the best interest of the cooperatives was the monitoring of business activities of the Board of Directors, the management, and employees. These activities were monitored because they could affect the decisions of the board as well as the implementation of the programs and projects of the organization. The cooperatives expanded in half of the cases, the services and business activities using diversification. Through strategy, the cooperatives could sustain their operations in the competitive business environment. Protiviti (2006) states, "ERM broadens the focus of risk management to all significant sources of enterprise value."

Table 9 presents the summarized data on the extent to which the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank implemented strategies for risk management.

As shown by the general average of 3.14 based on the group general average of 3.17 from the Board Members, 3.11 from the committees, and 3.14 from the individual members, risk management systems were implemented to a Moderate Extent, by the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank.

Risk control measures were implemented generally to a Moderate Extent as shown by the factor average of 3.34 from the Board Members, 3.34 from the committees, and 3.31 from the individual members. An examination into the specific measures showed that some of them were implemented to a Great Extent, while the majority of the measures were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

As viewed by the three groups of respondents, the measures of considering the borrowers' capacity to pay in extending credit and considering the members' capital investment as a basis for determining the amount of loan were implemented to a Great Extent. The measures of hiring a collector to monitor, follow up, and make actual collections as well as the automatic deviation from an original plan (Plan A) by adopting an alternative plan (Plan B) to cope with the economic crisis were implemented to a Moderate Extent. On the other hand, the measure of fixing a maximum loanable amount for a single borrower was implemented to a Great Extent. The measures of instituting legal action for delinquent and non-paying borrowers and accelerating the collection of receivables to avoid financial crisis were implemented to a Moderate Extent while enforcing stricter measures for screening loan applicants were viewed by the Board Members and the committees to be implemented to a Great Extent and by the individual members to be implemented to a Moderate Extent.

Strategies of loss financing were implemented to a Moderate Extent by the cooperatives as indicated by the factor average of 2.92 based on the group average of 2.95 from the Board Members, 2.87 from the committees, and 2.93 from the individual members, although one strategy was implemented to a Less Extent. This strategy consisted of establishing a retirement fund for employees of the cooperatives. Implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of allocating annually an optional fund for the cooperative and allocating annually for the Education and Training Fund to finance the training expenses of the cooperative.

Viewed by the Board Members as implemented to a Great Extent but by the committees and the individual members as implemented to a Moderate Extent was the measure of allocating annually for the General Reserve Fund to absorb possible losses on operations. Implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of providing an allowance for bad debts to absorb possible losses on loans, requiring a bond of accountable officers of the cooperatives, covering the borrowers by loan protection insurance in case of death, and covering facilities and equipment by insurance.

Internal risk reduction strategies were generally implemented to a Moderate Extent, as revealed by the factor average of 3.17 based on the group average of 3.23 from the Board Members, 3.11 from the committees, and 3.18 from the individual members. Three strategies, however, were implemented to a Great Extent. These strategies included submitting the cooperative to a yearly audit by the Audit and Inventory Committee, analyzing the financial statements and other monthly data to detect potential problems, and observing proper internal control systems in the cooperative.

The rest of the strategies were implemented in the cooperatives to a Moderate Extent. These strategies included providing the employees with appropriate insurance coverage as required by law, giving salaries to employees with the minimum as required by law, mentoring selected employees to fill up future vacancies in technical positions, monitoring conflict of interest within the board, management, and staff, and engaging in diversified cooperative services and activities.

Table 10 presents data on the implementation of control in the member cooperatives through the statement of success indicators.

As revealed by the factor average of 3.06 based on the group average of 3.06 from the Board Members, 3.07 from the committees, and 3.06 from the individual members, control practices were implemented to a Moderate Extent in the member cooperatives.

Specifically implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of requiring an increase in the profits of the cooperatives by ten to fifteen percent as compared to the previous year, as shown by the item average of 3.23 based on the weighted mean of 3.26 from the Board Members, 3.22 from the committees, and 3.22 from the individual members; requiring an increase in assets by more than twenty-five percent as compared to the previous year, as indicated by the item average of 3.03 based on the weighted mean of 3.04 from the Board Members, 3.01 from the committees, and 3.03 from the individual members; targeting a reserve fund of more than ten percent of net surplus, as indicated by the item average of 3.17 based on the weighted mean of 3.14 from the Board Members, 3.18 from the committees, and 3.18 from the individual members; and requiring an increase in the number of members or clientele by more than twenty percent as compared to the previous year, as disclosed by the item average of 2.97 based on the weighted mean of 2.87 from the Board Members, 2.95 from the committees, and 3.08 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that control practices through the use of indicators for the increase in revenue were used in the number of cooperatives to a limited extent. In an interview with the various Teachers' Cooperatives, some of the committees and individual members revealed that increases in profits of the cooperatives were aspired, but difficult to attain because all increases in revenues would depend on the volume of business. The same members also declared that the success indicators could be possibly stated in a development plan, but most of the cooperatives did not formulate development plans. These statements were made during the meetings, but they would have the full force of obligation if they were placed in the development plans of the cooperatives (Interview with the Teachers' Cooperatives on December 7-8, 2004).

Also, the use of indicators for the increase in assets was used by cooperatives to a limited extent. The inclusion of the increase in resources of the cooperatives in their action plans could trigger the management to struggle and exert more effort for the attainment of such an objective. An increase in assets was one of the barometers used by financial institutions in assessing the growth and development of cooperatives.

Likewise, the setting up of a target for the increase in reserve funds was made to a limited extent. The objective of augmenting the reserve fund could enhance the stability of the cooperatives. The Cooperative Code provided that at least ten percent (10%) of the net surplus of the cooperative should be set aside for the purpose. Furthermore, the objective of membership expansion by cooperative shareholders was also considered to a limited extent. This target was very necessary to increase the volume of patronage from the members which could eventually result in profitability. This strategy could also cause an increase in the capitalization of cooperatives.

To a Moderate Extent, more measures were implemented for control. These measures included maintaining a past due rate of not more than twenty-five percent, as revealed by the item average of 2.95 based on the weighted mean of 2.94 from the Board Members, 2.96 from the committees, and 2.95 from the individual members; targeting an increase in capital by at least twenty-five percent as compared to the previous year, as disclosed by the item average of 3.03 based on the weighted mean of 3.01 from the Board

Members, 3.08 from the cooperatives, and 3.00 from the individual member; requiring a decrease in the operating cost of the cooperatives by five percent as compared to the previous year, as indicated by the item average of 3.00 based on the weighted mean of 3.05 from the Board Members, 3.02 from the cooperatives, and 2.92 from the individual members; and maintaining a collection rate of at least seventy-five percent of the amounts due and collectible, as revealed by the item average of 3.14 based on the weighted mean of 3.17 from the Board Members, 3.13 from the committees, and 3.12 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that statement of success indicators for the purpose of guiding and controlling operations of cooperatives were made, but to a limited extent. Controls were made to a limited extent, on the past due borrowers of cooperatives. If this control would be stated categorically by the cooperatives, it would guide the employees to intensify the collection in order to reduce the borrowers' delinquency. Past due reduction should be focused by cooperatives so that they could maintain their best liquidity position. Likewise, any strategy for the increase in capital would improve the financial status of the cooperatives. However, this success indicator was stated to a limited extent in the plans of the cooperatives which were discussed during the meetings with cooperative leaders. Furthermore, the parameters of reducing the operating costs were also considered to a limited extent since many cooperatives did not engage in formal planning. This strategy was considered vital to the business operation because the effect of this objective could mean more profits of the cooperative. Finally, the improvement of collection rate especially on credit operations was included in the plans of cooperatives to a limited extent. This was attributed to the fact that some of the cooperatives had no collectors to focus on the collection of receivables. Success indicators are values or standards used as a point of reference for the extent to which the objectives of an organization are met. Success indicators are sets of accomplishments that may be expected of an individual or a group. In some instances, objectives may be used as success indicators (Rue and Byars, 2002).

Table 11 presents data on the implementation of operations control practices through performance monitoring in the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank.

As indicated by the factor average of 3.36 based on the group average of 3.40 from the Board Members, 3.33 from the committees, and 3.24 from the individual members, control practices through performance monitoring were implemented to a Moderate Extent. Some measures, were, however implemented to a Great Extent. The measure of submitting the cooperative to performance and fiscal audit by an external auditor was implemented to a Great Extent, as indicated by the item average of 3.46 based on the weighted mean of 3.55 from the Board Members, 3.41 from the committees, and 2.43 from the individual members.

This finding denoted that in the majority of cases, the cooperatives availed the services of external auditors to determine the reliability of their financial statements. The purpose of engaging in external auditors was to countercheck the findings of the Audit and Inventory Committee of cooperatives. In this manner, control would be imposed, because the external auditors, being disinterested parties to the cooperatives, could present an objective view of the financial standing of the cooperatives.

Implemented to a Moderate Extent by the member cooperatives were the measures of conducting a semi-annual performance evaluation of employees, as indicated by the item average of 2.98 based on the weighted mean of 3.01 from the Board Members, 2.88 from the committees, and 3.05 from the individual members; and monitoring the trend of the members' patronage to cooperative services, as shown by the item average of 3.30 based on the weighted mean of 3.33 from the Board Members, 3.35 from the committee, and 3.22 from the individual members.

From these findings, it could be inferred that while controls were made through the evaluation of employees' performance, this measure was implemented to a limited extent. The objective of this control measure was to determine the efficiency and effectiveness of employees especially in the performance of their job duties and responsibilities. According to the members of government employees' cooperatives, the evaluation of personnel was not formally done because some cooperatives did not have performance evaluation instruments. On the other hand, the monitoring of the trend in the patronage of cooperative services was done, but to a limited extent. This method was very necessary because the volume of business of cooperatives largely depended on the involvement and participation of the members. The officers of the government employees' cooperatives noted that the monitoring of patronage was not easy because of the lack of personnel. In other words, they could conduct monitoring activities to a limited extent.

To a Moderate Extent, the measure of monitoring the amortization payments of member borrowers was implemented, as indicated by the item average of 3.39. The weighted mean of 3.45 from the Board Members indicated their view that this measure was taken to a Great Extent. It was viewed as implemented to a Moderate Extent by the committees, who rated it 3.38, and by the individual members, who rated it 3.35.

Regarding the monitoring activities of cooperatives especially on the amortization payments of borrowers, the Board of Directors viewed its implementation to a majority of cases, while the committees and individual members considered the measure as implemented to a limited extent.

The disparity in the responses of the three groups could be attributed to the difference in the positions that they occupied in their respective cooperatives. The board responded that the monitoring of amortization was done in the majority of cases, because this measure was part of their duties and responsibilities. The other two groups were aware of the implementation of monitoring practices, but because they had not taken charge of monitoring duties, they indicated that this measure was taken to a limited extent.

As indicated by the item average of 3.41, the measure of monitoring compliance of the by-laws, rules, and regulations of the cooperative was implemented to a Great Extent. The weighted mean of 3.41 from the Board Members and 3.43 from the committees showed that they viewed this measure to be implemented to a Great Extent. The weighted mean of 3.38 from the individual members indicated that they perceived this measure to be implemented to a Moderate Extent.

Based on this finding, the measure of monitoring compliance of the by-laws, rules and regulations of the cooperatives was implemented in the majority of cases specifically as viewed by the Board of Directors and the committees. However, it was viewed by the individual members in half of the cases. The disparity of the responses of the Board Members and the committees on one hand and the individual members on the other,

could be attributed to the interest which they had in connection with compliance of the by-laws, rules and regulations. The Board of Directors were interested in the members' compliance, therefore monitored it very well. The individual members on the other hand, viewed the measure from the passive perspective of a group from whom compliance was required, therefore viewed the measure as implemented to a limited extent.

Implemented to a Great Extent were the measures of monitoring submission and compliance of annual reports and audited financial statements to the Cooperative Development Authority, as indicated by the item average of 3.51 based on the weighted mean of 3.60 from the Board Members, 3.45 from the committees, and 3.47 from the individual members; and identifying active and inactive members of the cooperative, as disclosed by the item average of 3.44 based on the weighted mean of 3.44 from the Board Members, 3.42 from the committees, and 3.45 from the individual members.

Implied by these findings was the control imposed on operations by the strict compliance of the requirements of the law. The submission of annual reports was mandated under Article 54 of Republic Act 6938, otherwise known as the Cooperative Code of the Philippines. Thus, the required annual reports and audited financial statements were submitted to the Cooperative Development Authority in the majority of cases by the shareholder cooperatives. Also, the cooperatives identified the active and inactive individual members in the majority of cases. This measure was useful in determining the collection of unpaid subscriptions, monitoring of accounts, and the distribution of dividends to cooperative members. In addition, the present number of members could be the basis for membership expansion of the cooperatives.

Table 12 contains data on the implementation of operations control practices through the correction of deviation from standards among the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank.

As indicated by the factor average of 3.25 based on the group average of 3.36 from the Board Members, 3.19 from the committees, and 3.21 from the individual members, control practices through the correction of deviation from standards were implemented, to a Moderate Extent, in the member cooperatives.

Specifically, the item average of 3.39 indicated that the measure of suggesting techniques of collecting the obligations of individual members was implemented to a Moderate Extent. The weighted mean of 3.49 from the Board of Directors denoted that they viewed this measure as implemented to a Great Extent. The view that it was implemented to a Moderate Extent was held by the committees, as revealed by the weighted mean of 3.34 and by the individual members, as indicated by the item average of 3.34.

The Board of Directors viewed in the majority of cases, that officers suggested ways and means of collecting the problematic accounts of borrowers, while the committees and individual members perceived the measure as implemented in half of the cases. The responses of the Board of Directors differed from those of the committees and the individual members because the former were responsible for identifying innovative techniques of collecting the members' obligations. The Board Members were more concerned with the use of various collection strategies and enforcing the rules in order to maintain a good financial position in their respective cooperatives.

As disclosed by the item average of 3.48 based on the weighted mean of 3.50 from the Board Members, 3.43 from the committees, and 3.50 from the individual members, the practice of requesting that all committees regularly perform their functions was implemented to a Great Extent.

From this finding, it could be inferred that in the majority of cases, the cooperatives rectified the deviations from standards by reminding the various committees of their duties and responsibilities. In other words, emphasis was made on the performance of committee obligations in order to strengthen their respective organizations and to provide direction to the movement. These committees include the Audit and Inventory Committee, Credit Committee, Education and Training Committee and Election Committee as stated in the by-laws of the cooperatives.

As disclosed by the item average of 3.45, the practice of requiring the members to attend the Pre-Membership Education Seminar on the cooperative was implemented to a Great Extent. The weighted mean of 3.59 from the Board of Directors denoted their view that this practice was implemented to a Great Extent. The weighted mean of 3.36 from the committees indicated their view that this practice was implemented to a Moderate Extent, while the weighted mean of 3.41 from the individual members showed their view that this practice was implemented to a Great Extent.

On the basis of this finding, the Board of Directors together with the individual members had an opposing view with that of the committees. For the Board of Directors and individual members, the measure was implemented in the majority of cases, while the committees viewed that the measure was made in half of the cases.

The disparity of the responses of the Board of Directors and individual members on one hand and the committees on the other was due mainly to the responsibilities assumed by them. The Board Members were concerned with the Pre-Membership Education Seminar, since they were responsible for the conduct of this seminar. The individual members knew that his seminar was required for membership. The group that was most concerned was that which took charge of membership. Thus, the committees, while performing their respective assignments, may not have been concerned with membership. As a result, they viewed this practice as implemented to a limited extent.

As indicated by the item average of 3.15 based on the weighted mean of 3.23 from the Board Members, 3.10 from the committees, and 3.13 from the individual members, the practice of proposing sanctions for directors and officers who neglect their duties was implemented to a Moderate Extent.

This finding implied that to a limited extent, penalties were meted out to the directors and officers who reneged their duties and responsibilities to the cooperatives. This measure was implemented in order to strengthen the cooperatives especially those with irresponsible and disloyal directors. The disciplinary actions towards the directors and officers were mandated by virtue of the provisions of Article 46 and 49 of Republic Act 6938.

As indicated by the item average of 3.36, the practice of correcting the ways in which records were kept by the cooperatives was implemented to a Moderate Extent. The weighted mean of 3.49 indicated the Board Members' view that this practice was implemented to a Great Extent. It was viewed as implemented to a Moderate Extent by the committees, as revealed by the weighted mean of 3.32 and the individual members, as revealed by the weighted mean of 3.26.

Based on this finding, the Board of Directors on one hand and the committees and individual members on the other hand, had different views in correcting the recording systems of the cooperatives. For the Board Members, they viewed as implemented in the majority of cases, while for the committees and individual members, they perceived the measure as done in half of the cases.

The response of the Board Members differed from that of the committees and the individual members according to the extent of their awareness regarding the inspection of records that was conducted by the Board Members. Record-keeping was given much importance by the Board Members, who exerted much effort to make corrections on the record-keeping techniques of cooperatives. Clarity of records could facilitate the detection of fraud. For this reason, the Board of Directors were very much concerned with correct record-keeping.

Implemented to a Moderate Extent were the practice of imposing penalties for non-attendance in membership meetings, as shown by the item average of 2.97 based on the weighted mean of 3.15 from the Board Members, 2.84 from the committees, and 2.92 from the individual members; and suggesting ways of terminating directors or officers whose pecuniary interests were in conflict with their duties toward the cooperative, as disclosed by the item average of 2.99 based on the weighted mean of 3.06 from the Board Members, 2.97 from the committees, and 2.94 from the individual members.

Implied by these findings were the facts that the imposition of sanctions for non-attendance to membership meetings and the application of termination measures to directors and officers were implemented to a limited extent in the cooperatives. Penalties were not usually imposed to the members, since membership meetings could be a measure of the members' interest in the organization. However, termination of membership could even be imposed in accordance with the provisions of Article 31 of Republic Act 6938. In the case of directors and officers whose activities and interests were in conflict with the cooperative, could be removed by a vote of two-thirds (2/3) of the voting members present and constituting a quorum, in a regular or special general assembly meeting called for the purpose as provided by law. This is consistent to Gobenciong (2001) study which revealed that the deputized disaster management coordinators demonstrated risk management capabilities through deviation from the plan and deviation from past experiences to a Moderate Extent. They manifested risk management capabilities through opportunity finding to a Great Extent.

Table 13 presents summarized data on the implementation of operations control practices in the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank.

As shown by the general average of 3.22 based on the group general average of 3.27 from the Board Members, 3.20 from the committees, and 3.20 from the individual members, operations control practices were implemented in the member cooperatives to a Moderate Extent.

The statement of success indicators was implemented to a Moderate Extent, as indicated by the factor average of 3.06 based on the group average of 3.06 from the Board Members, 3.07 from the committees, and 3.06 from the individual members.

Specifically implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of requiring an increase in the profits of the cooperatives by ten to fifteen percent as compared to the previous year, requiring an increase in assets by more than twenty-five percent as

compared to the previous year, requiring an increase in assets by more than twenty-five percent as compared to the previous year, targeting a reserve fund of more than ten percent of the net surplus, and requiring an increase in the number of members or clients by more than twenty percent as compared to the previous year. Also implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of maintaining a past due rate of not more than twenty-five percent, targeting an increase in capital by at least twenty-five percent as compared to the previous year, requiring a decrease in the operating cost of the cooperative by five percent as compared to the previous year, and maintaining a collection rate of at least seventy-five percent of the amounts due and collectible.

The implementation of performance monitoring was made to a Moderate Extent, as revealed by the factor average of 3.36 based on the group average of 3.40 from the Board Members, 3.33 from the committees, and 3.34 from the individual members. There were, however some measures that were implemented to a Great Extent. The practice of submitting the cooperative to performance and fiscal audit by an external auditor was implemented to a Great Extent. Implemented to a Moderate Extent were the practices of conducting a semi-annual performance evaluation of employees and monitoring the trend of the members' patronage to cooperative services.

The practice of monitoring the amortization payments of member borrowers was viewed by the Board Members as implemented to a Great Extent and by the committees and individual members as implemented to a Moderate Extent. The practice of monitoring compliance of the by-laws, rules, and regulations of the cooperative was viewed by the Board Members and the committees as implemented to a Great Extent and by the individual members as viewed to a Moderate Extent. Implemented to a Great Extent were the practice of monitoring submission and compliance of annual reports and audited financial statements to the Cooperative Development Authority and identifying active and inactive members of the cooperative.

Operations control practices through the correction of deviations from standards were implemented to a Moderate Extent, as disclosed by the factor average of 3.25 based on the group average of 3.36 from the Board Members, 3.19 from the committees, and 3.21 from the individual members.

Viewed by the Board Members as implemented to a Great Extent and by the committees and individual members as implemented to a Moderate Extent was the practice of suggesting techniques of collecting the obligations of individual members, while all of the three groups viewed the practice of requesting that all committees regularly perform their functions as implemented to a Great Extent. The practice of requiring the members to attend the Pre-Membership Education Seminar on Cooperatives was viewed by the Board Members and the individual members as implemented to a Great Extent and by the committees as implemented to a Moderate Extent. Viewed by all groups as implemented to a Moderate Extent was the practice of proposing sanctions for directors and officers who neglect their duties and responsibilities.

The practice of correcting the ways in which records were kept by the cooperatives was viewed by the directors as implemented to a Great Extent and by the committees and individual members as implemented to a Moderate Extent. The practices of imposing penalties for non-attendance to membership meetings and suggesting ways of terminating directors or officers whose pecuniary interests are in conflict with their duties toward the cooperative were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

As shown in **Table 14**, there was no significant correlation between the implementation of goal setting and risk control measures, as shown by the computed r value of 0.599, loss financing, as shown by the computed r value of 0.562, and internal risk reduction, as revealed by the computed r value of 0.630, all of which were less than 0.707, the region of rejection at six degrees of freedom.

These findings meant that goal setting in the corporate governance did not have any effect on the risk control measures, loss financing schemes, and internal risk reduction. Thus, these risk management systems could not be traced to the goal setting measures used by the member cooperatives.

There was a significant correlation between the implementation of organizational strategies and the risk control measures used by the cooperatives, as shown by the computed r value of 0.832, but there was no significant correlation between the organizational strategies implemented by the cooperatives and their loss financing schemes, as indicated by the computed r value of 0.672. However, there was a significant correlation between organizational strategies and internal risk reduction, as indicated by the computed r value of 0.819.

These findings revealed that the organizational strategies used by the member cooperatives had effects on the risk control measures used by the cooperatives as well as on the internal risk reduction measures used by them. However, their organizational strategies did not affect the loss financing schemes used by the cooperatives.

There was a significant correlation between the member cooperatives' implementation of administrative policies and procedures and their risk control measures, as revealed by the computed r value of 0.768, but there was no significant correlation between the implementation of administrative policies and procedures and their loss financing schemes, as revealed by the computed r value of 0.699. There was a significant correlation in the implementation of administrative policies and procedures and their internal risk reduction measures, as revealed by the computed r value of 0.751.

These findings showed that the aspect of governance consisting of administrative policies and procedures affected the risk control measures of the cooperatives as well as the internal risk reduction measures used by them. The administrative policies and procedures did not affect their loss financing schemes.

There was a significant correlation between the member cooperatives' implementation of feedback systems and their risk control measures, as revealed by the computed r value of 0.857; their loss financing measures, as shown by the computed r value of 0.816; and internal risk reduction measures, as revealed by the computed r value 0.853.

These findings revealed that the feedback systems of the cooperatives generally provided for the discussion of the implementation of risk control measures, loss financing schemes, and internal risk reduction. Thus, feedback regarding the ways to manage risk was solicited from the members.

Taking into consideration the results of the Pearson r test, the first null hypothesis was Accepted when applied to goal setting and the factors of risk management; Rejected when applied to the relationship between organizational strategies, and administrative policies and procedures on one hand and risk control measures and internal risk reduction on the other; Accepted when applied to the factors of corporate governance and loss

financing, and Rejected when applied to feedback systems and the risk management measures.

As revealed in **Table 15**, there was no significant correlation between the implementation of goal setting and the statement of success indicators, as revealed by the computed r value of 0.519, and performance monitoring, as shown by the computed r value of 0.606. There was a significant correlation between the implementation of goal setting and deviation from standards, as shown by the computed r value of 0.863.

These findings revealed that the implementation of goal setting had no connection with the statement of success indicators and performance monitoring in the member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank. Thus, while the goals provided for deviation from standards, they did not provided for the other two practices.

There was a significant correlation between the implementation of organizational strategies and the statements of success indicators, as shown by the computed r value of 0.784 and performance monitoring as shown by the computed r value of 0.762. There was no significant correlation between the implementation of organizational strategies and deviation from standards, as indicated by the computed r value of 0.634.

These findings showed that the organizational strategies included the statement of success indicators and performance monitoring. No measures for deviating from standards were taken.

There was a significant correlation between the implementation of administrative policies and procedures and the statement of success indicators, as shown by the computed r value of 0.744. There was no significant correlation between the implementation of administrative policies and procedures and performance monitoring, as shown by the computed r value of 0.012, and deviation from standards, as revealed by the computed r value of 0.642.

These findings showed that while the administrative policies provided for the statement of success indicators, the measures for monitoring performance and deviation from standards were implemented.

There was no significant correlation between the member cooperatives' implementation of feedback systems and the statement of success indicators, as shown by the computed r value of 0.692. There was a significant correlation between the implementation of feedback systems and performance monitoring measures, as revealed by the computed r value of 0.840 and deviation from standards as revealed by the computed r value of 0.766. These findings implied that feedback was not solicited regarding the statement of success indicators. However feedback was solicited on performance monitoring and deviation from standards.

Based on the Pearson r test, the second null hypothesis was Accepted when applied to goal setting and feedback on one hand and the statement of success indicators on the other hand and between goal setting and administrative policies and procedures on one hand and performance monitoring on the other hand. The null hypothesis was Accepted when applied to the implementation of organizational strategies and administrative policies and procedures on one hand and deviation from standards on the other hand. The null hypothesis was Rejected when applied to the correlation between the implementation of organizational strategies and administrative policies and procedures on one hand and the statement of success indicators on the other hand. The

null hypothesis was Rejected when applied to goal setting and deviation from standards and organizational strategies and performance monitoring, as well as feedback systems and performance monitoring.

Table 16 presents the program for improving the corporate governance of cooperatives. This program is based on the database presented below.

Data Base: Table 1 shows that according to the evaluation of the committees and the individual members, thrift and savings among the members were encouraged to a Moderate Extent in the cooperatives, and that to a Moderate Extent, as evaluated by the three groups, the cooperatives provided social services to its members and increased the volume of business of the cooperatives.

Table 2 shows that to a Moderate Extent training was provided annually to the directors, committees and employees; the latest technology in the processing of transactions was adopted, and continuous membership expansion was implemented.

Table 3 shows that all administrative policies and procedures were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

Table 4 discloses that all feedback systems were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

Table 17 presents the program for revitalization of risk management systems. This program is based on the database presented below.

Data Base: Table 6, on risk control measures, shows that to a Moderate Extent, the cooperatives implemented the measures of hiring a collector to monitor, follow up, and make actual collections; automatically deviating from an original plan (Plan A) by adopting an alternative plan (Plan B) to cope with economic crisis; instituting legal action for delinquent and non-paying borrowers; and accelerating the collection of receivables to avoid financial crisis.

Table 7 reveals that various loss financing measures were implemented to a Moderate Extent by the cooperatives. Table 8 shows that five out of eight measures of internal risk reduction were implemented to a Moderate Extent. These measures included providing employees with adequate insurance coverage as required by law, giving salaries to employees with the minimum required by law, mentoring selected employees to fill up future vacancies in technical positions, monitoring conflicts of business interest within the Board, the management, and the staff, and engaging in diversified cooperative services and activities.

Table 18 presents the program for redirection of operations control. This program is based on the database presented below.

Data Base: Table 10 shows that to a Moderate Extent, success indicators such as the increase of the profits of the cooperative by ten to fifteen percent, requiring an increase in assets by more than 25 percent as compared to those of the previous year, aiming for a reserve fund of more than ten percent of the net surplus, and requiring an increase in membership and clientele as compared to the previous year were implemented. Also implemented to a Moderate Extent were the measures of maintaining a past due rate of not more than twenty-five percent,

targeting an increase in capital by at least twenty-five percent as compared to the previous year, requiring a decrease in the operating cost of the cooperative by five percent as compared to the previous year, and maintaining a collection rate of at least 75 percent of the amounts due and collectible.

Table 11 shows that the measures of conducting a semi-annual performance evaluation of employees and monitoring the trend of the members' patronage to cooperative services were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

Table 12 reveals that the measures of proposing sanctions for directors and officers who neglect their duties, imposing penalties for non-attendance in membership meetings, and suggesting ways of terminating directors and officers whose pecuniary interests are in conflict with their duties toward the cooperative were implemented to a Moderate Extent.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that while the institutional member cooperatives of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank operated successfully, redirections in their implementation of corporate governance measures, risk management systems, and operations control practices were needed to be effective in rendering cooperative services to their members.

Recommendations

In the context of the findings of the study, the researcher recommends:

1. That the development program entitled "Cooperatives for the Revitalization of Economic Endeavor for Development (CREED) be adopted for implementation.
2. That for the purpose of expanding membership in the cooperatives, the directors and officers should wage a massive campaign in their respective institutions.
3. That the directors and officers of the institutional members of the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank attend seminars on the implementation of administrative policies and procedures in the organization.
4. That the institutional member cooperatives write, publish, and issue a manual for employees in order to guide the cooperatives toward better operations.
5. That the institutional member cooperatives maintain adequate reserve funds for sustainability in case of losses in operations.

Further recommendations. Topics that future researchers may consider for future study are recommended. They are the following:

1. Community Organizations, Cooperativism, and Community Action in Dipolog City: Bases for a Development Program.
2. Profitability, Job Generation Capabilities and Financial Management Strategies of the Cooperatives of Zamboanga del Norte: Proposals for Enrichment.
3. Customer Relations and Adjustments of Service Features to Cultural Diversity in the Zamboanga del Norte Cooperative Bank: Bases for Proposals to the Management.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author(s) have stated that they have no potential conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article. The authors accomplished this study in compliance with the research ethics protocol. Informed consent was given to the respondents before the research instrument was distributed. The data were treated with the utmost confidentiality.

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